

¿Is there in the universe, a celestial body similar to the earth?

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ABSTRACT

Since ancient times, humanity has been curious about the possibility of other worlds similar to Earth in the vast universe. While this question has intrigued scientists and dreamers alike, in recent years we have gained valuable clues thanks to technological advances and space missions. One of the most exciting destinations in our search for Earth-like celestial bodies is Titan, Saturn's largest moon. Although Titan differs in several fundamental aspects from our planet, it possesses amazing features that have sparked the interest and imagination of scientists. With its dense atmosphere composed mainly of nitrogen and its presence of liquids in the form of lakes and seas, including hydrocarbons such as methane and ethane, Titan has become a key study object for understanding planetary processes and the possibility of life in extraterrestrial environments. different from those we know on Earth. In this introduction, we'll explore Titan's fascinating features and how they bring us closer to answering the fundamental question: Is there an Earth-like celestial body in the universe?

Keywords: celestial body, universe, Earth, exoplanets, extraterrestrial life, atmosphere, habitable zone, similarities, habitable planets, space exploration.

1. INTRODUCTION

Today we persistently search for traces of life in systems parallel to our solar system; on planets and natural satellites distant from earth in our solar system, and our attention, too, is focused beyond our solar system, into the depths of the abyss in space. However, we have forgotten that a few centuries ago a unique celestial body was discovered, located relatively close to us, on the planet Saturn, a moon where clouds float and rain falls in its atmosphere, where there are abundant rivers flowing on the surface, gathering in lakes and seas; however, the conditions for human life on this moon, for the inhabitants of the earth, in this amazing celestial body are deadly; its surface is dominated by incredible cold. The name of this satellite of Saturn is Titan.

Uncertainty has always existed as to whether there is more life in the universe, which is why scientists from NASA and the European Space Agency, after some investigations carried out on the surface of Titan, Saturn's largest moon, determined that the Earth does not. It is the only planet that can host human and animal life, since Titan shows some atmospheric conditions and meteorological processes similar to those of Earth, there are winds, rains and a dense atmosphere, very similar to that of our planet, which is why which scientists expect to find on said satellite, life like ours, since Titan is practically the twin celestial body of Earth.

Titan is one of the best-known moons in the solar system, the largest of the moons of the planet Saturn, it is the second largest moon in the solar system after Ganymede, the moon of the planet Jupiter; It is larger than the planets Pluto and Mercury. It has a planetary atmosphere that is denser than those of Mercury, Earth, Mars and Pluto, its atmosphere contains mainly molecular nitrogen (90%) and approximately 6% methane and complex hydrocarbon compounds, it presents some characteristics similar to the atmosphere of Earth, with a surface pressure 50% greater than Earth's, has a diameter 50% greater than our Moon and is 80% more massive, its size is greater than that of the planet Mercury, although its mass is 40% less, its atmospheric pressure is about 1.6 bars, 60% greater than that of Earth.

Titan, Saturn's largest moon, has captivated our imaginations for decades due to its fascinating and mysterious environment. With a dense, mostly nitrogenous atmosphere, and the presence of liquids on its surface, including hydrocarbon lakes and seas, Titan has become a target of interest for scientists and astronomers seeking to better understand the potential for life elsewhere in the solar system.

As space exploration continues to advance, we have been asking ourselves the question: is it possible to live on Titan? This moon presents some unique challenges and extreme conditions, but it also offers a number of factors that could make it a viable destination for human colonization.

One of the most promising aspects of Titan is its abundance of organic compounds, building blocks for life as we know it. These compounds, combined with the presence of frozen water and the energy provided by the Sun, could provide the necessary ingredients to support an extraterrestrial life form or even be used by humans in the distant future.

However, adapting to Titan's conditions would be a considerable challenge. The average temperature of its surface is extremely cold, hovering around -290 degrees Fahrenheit (-179 degrees Celsius), which would require the development of suitable technologies and space suits to survive in such a frigid environment.

In addition, Titan's dense atmosphere has low oxygen pressure, which means that humans could not breathe the air directly. Installation of life support systems and oxygen generation would be required to maintain a breathable atmosphere in enclosed habitats.

Despite these challenges, the possibility of living on Titan piques the interest and curiosity of scientists and space explorers. Colonization of this moon could offer a unique opportunity to study extraterrestrial life forms and expand our horizons as a species.

As technology advances and space exploration intensifies, perhaps one day we will see manned missions to Titan and the construction of human bases on its surface. Although it is a long-term goal, the potential of living on this intriguing and mystery-filled moon invites us to dream of a future in which humans can settle in places beyond our own planet.

2. DIFFERENCES AND SIMILARITIES BETWEEN EARTH AND TITAN

COMPARISON CHART BETWEEN EARTH AND SATURN'S SATELLITE, TITAN

DESCRIPTION	
PLANET EARTH	TITAN, SATELLITE OF SATURN
<p>Planet Earth</p> <p>The Earth was formed around 4.55 billion years ago, from the material from which the rest of the solar system was made, which was initially a stellar cloud of gases and cosmic dust. The formation of the planet took between 10 and 20 million years, as its surface cooled and the cloud of gases that is today's atmosphere accumulated around it.</p> <p>The Earth is the fifth planet in the solar system in terms of size, it has a spherical shape with a slight flattening at the poles. It has the highest density in the solar system.</p>	<p>Titan, satellite of Saturn</p> <p>Age: 4,003 billion years</p> <p>Discovery date: March 25, 1655</p> <p>Discoverer: Christiaan Huygens</p> <p>Average distance from Saturn: (km) 1,221,850</p>
ORBITAL ELEMENTS	
<p>They are the necessary parameters (six Keplerian elements) to uniquely identify the specific orbit of a celestial body. In celestial mechanics these elements are considered in two-body systems using a Kepler orbit (idealized mathematical approximation of the orbit at a given time.)</p> <p>The eccentricity e, is a number from 0 to 1, which gives the shape of the orbit. For a circle $e = 0$, values greater than 0 provide progressively flatter rings, up to $e = 1$ where the ellipse stretches to infinity and becomes a parabola.</p> <p>In the case of the Titan satellite, its orbital elements tend to change over time, the evolution of its orbital elements takes place mainly due to the gravitational force exerted by the planet Saturn on it, this change can also be due to other forces, including: the gravitational force exerted by other bodies (Sun, Saturn's Rings, etc.), the atmospheric resistance in low orbits, the pressure of solar radiation, in addition these changes can be generated due to the lack of sphericity of Titan, rubbing with the remnants of the atmosphere, the expulsion of methane gas and other gases, and the fact that electromagnetic forces introduce small non-gravitational forces that must be considered to explain their movement.</p>	
<p>The Earth</p> <p>The Earth's axis of rotation is tilted by approximately 23.5 degrees. It is because of this inclination that each hemisphere receives the Sun's rays more directly every six months (thus causing the change of weather seasons).</p> <p>The Earth's orbit has an Eccentricity $e = 0.0068$</p> <p>Orbital inclination 7.155° with the equator of the Sun and 1.57869° with respect to the unchanging plane.</p> <p>Semimajor axis 149 598 261 km</p> <p>Orbital Eccentricity 0.01671123</p>	<p>Titan</p> <p>Orbital inclination 0.34854°</p> <p>Semi-major axis 1,221,870 km</p> <p>Orbital Eccentricity 0.028 880</p> <p>Derived orbital elements</p> <p>Periastrum or perihelion 1,186,680 kilometers</p> <p>Apoastro or aphelion 1,257,060 kilometers</p> <p>Rotational Period 15,945 42 (15 d 22 h 41 m 27 s) $\approx$ 16 days</p> <p>Sidereal orbital period 15.945 42</p> <p>Seasons:</p>

Derived orbital elements Periastrum or perihelion 147,098,290 km Apoastro or aphelion 152 098 232 km Rotational Period 23 h 56 m 4.100 s) ≈ 1 day Axial tilt 23°26'21" 0,4119	Titan, like Earth, has seasons. The effective obliquity of the sun's rays is 26.7°. There the day lasts the equivalent of 15.9 Earth days and each season approximately 2,687 Earth days (about 7.4 years).
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ATMOSPHERE

The Earth The atmosphere is made up of a mixture of gases, mainly nitrogen, oxygen, argon and carbon dioxide. It reaches more than 500 km above the surface of the planet. Atmospheric gases become thinner as you go up. The atmosphere continues to become less and less dense, until it mixes with outer space.	Titan Titan is the moon of the planet Saturn that presents the best conditions to host extraterrestrial microbial life, since it is the only celestial body with a dense atmosphere, made up of nitrogen, and liquid lakes on its surface, made up of hydrocarbons such as methane and ethane. Titan's air is composed primarily of nitrogen with other hydrocarbons that give Titan its characteristic orange hue. These hydrocarbons are the building blocks that constitute the amino acids necessary for the formation of life. Many of the hydrocarbons in the atmosphere rain or snow on the surface, and changes in their extent and even composition have been observed over the past 30 years. Scientists believe that Titan's environment is similar to what Earth had before life began putting oxygen into the atmosphere.
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GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS

The Earth The Earth is the third planet in the solar system starting from the Sun, located between Venus and Mars, it is a rocky planet, with a solid surface and a core of liquid metal (by action of heat and the pressure of its own gravity). It has a solid and active surface, with mountains, valleys, canyons, plains and much more. Earth is special because it is an ocean planet, with water covering 70% of its surface. According to our current knowledge, it is the only one that harbors life in the entire solar system.	Titan Titan, the largest satellite of Saturn and the second largest in the solar system after Ganymede. It can be considered a mini planet. It is the celestial body most similar to Earth, since it presents an atmosphere and some meteorological processes similar to Earth. There are meteorological phenomena that depend on the seasons and allow the formation and disappearance of lakes (between 10 and 100,000 km ²), mainly at the poles. Titan does not show topographic relief higher than 2,000 m in height. On Titan's surface you could walk without much effort, except for the effort needed to overcome some hurricane winds of up to 180 km/h; Titan's surface is relatively flat. Apart from Earth, it is the only known satellite where clear evidence of stable liquid bodies on the surface has been found.
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PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS

The Earth <table border="0"> <tr><td>Mass</td><td>5.9736 x 10²⁴ kg</td></tr> <tr><td>Magnitude (Vo)</td><td>8.28</td></tr> <tr><td>Volume</td><td>1.08321×10¹² km³</td></tr> <tr><td>Density</td><td>5.515 g/cm³</td></tr> <tr><td>Surface area</td><td>510 072 000 km²</td></tr> <tr><td>Equatorial radius</td><td>6378.1 km.</td></tr> <tr><td>Diameter</td><td>12,756 km</td></tr> <tr><td>Gravity</td><td>9.780327 m/s²</td></tr> <tr><td>Average Orbital Velocity</td><td>5580 m/sec</td></tr> <tr><td>Escape Velocity</td><td>11,186 km/s</td></tr> <tr><td>Rotation period Synchronous rotation</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Visual Geometric Albedo</td><td>0.367</td></tr> </table>	Mass	5.9736 x 10 ²⁴ kg	Magnitude (Vo)	8.28	Volume	1.08321×10 ¹² km ³	Density	5.515 g/cm ³	Surface area	510 072 000 km ²	Equatorial radius	6378.1 km.	Diameter	12,756 km	Gravity	9.780327 m/s ²	Average Orbital Velocity	5580 m/sec	Escape Velocity	11,186 km/s	Rotation period Synchronous rotation		Visual Geometric Albedo	0.367	Titan <table border="0"> <tr><td>Mass</td><td>1.345×10²³ kg</td></tr> <tr><td>Magnitude (Vo)</td><td>8.28</td></tr> <tr><td>Volume</td><td>7.16×10¹⁹ m³</td></tr> <tr><td>Density</td><td>1.88 g/cm³</td></tr> <tr><td>Surface area</td><td>8.34×10¹³ m²</td></tr> <tr><td>Radius</td><td>2 574 kilometers</td></tr> <tr><td>diameter</td><td>5150 km</td></tr> <tr><td>Gravity</td><td>1,352 m/s²</td></tr> <tr><td>Average Orbital Velocity</td><td>5580 m/sec</td></tr> <tr><td>Exhaust velocity</td><td>2650 m/s</td></tr> <tr><td>Rotation period Synchronous rotation</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Visual Geometric Albedo</td><td>0.21</td></tr> </table> <p>Saturn's enormous gravity creates strong tides in Titan's atmosphere, which is 400 times greater than Earth's on the Moon. Computer</p>	Mass	1.345×10 ²³ kg	Magnitude (Vo)	8.28	Volume	7.16×10 ¹⁹ m ³	Density	1.88 g/cm ³	Surface area	8.34×10 ¹³ m ²	Radius	2 574 kilometers	diameter	5150 km	Gravity	1,352 m/s ²	Average Orbital Velocity	5580 m/sec	Exhaust velocity	2650 m/s	Rotation period Synchronous rotation		Visual Geometric Albedo	0.21
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	<p>models reveal that these tides are responsible for Titan's near-surface winds.</p> <p>The reason why Titan's north pole has more lakes than the south pole is currently unknown; however, a recent theory suggests that it is due to the eccentricity of Saturn's orbit around the Sun, which causes methane to tend to concentrate in Titan's northern hemisphere.</p>
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ATMOSPHERIC CHARACTERISTICS

<p>The Earth</p> <p>Temperature Earth's normal temperature is 20 to 25 °C (293 to 298 °K).</p> <p>Atmospheric pressure 101.325 KPa Mean surface temperature 287.2 °K, or, 14.05 °C</p> <p>Composition The earth mass is made up of a diverse set of chemical elements. The most abundant elements are iron (32.1%), oxygen (30.1%), silicon (15.1%), magnesium (13.9%), sulfur (2.9%), nickel (1, 8%), calcium (1.5%) and aluminum (1.4%), leaving 1.2% for the rest of the elements.</p> <p>It is estimated that iron and nickel abound in its inner layers, which would be responsible for the generation of its magnetic field or magnetosphere.</p>	<p>Titan</p> <p>Temperature Titan is a moon with temperatures of -179 °C (-289 °F or 93.7 °K),</p> <p>Average surface temperature 179°C Atmospheric pressure 1.5 bar</p> <p>Composition Titan's surface temperature is high enough to maintain significant amounts of methane and nitrogen in the gaseous state, its atmosphere is composed of nitrogen (95%) and methane (5%), because it is too cold to maintain liquid water, in the surface presents methane and liquid ethane.</p> <p>Methane from Titan, due to continuous photochemical processes, is converted to ethane, acetylene, ethylene, and (when combined with nitrogen) hydrogen cyanide. The latter is an important compound as it is one of the building blocks of amino acids.</p>
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SURFACE

<p>The Earth</p> <p>The vast majority of the Earth's surface (70%) is covered with water and the remaining 30% is occupied by continental masses. However, below the water that fills the oceans, and the land and plants that cover the continents, the Earth's surface layer is made up of rocks.</p> <p>The Earth's crust is fractured into several large plates that move slowly relative to each other. Mountain ranges are formed when two plates collide and their edges are forced up. In addition, many other surface features are the result of moving plates. Plates move about one inch per year, so millions of years ago the continents and oceans were in different positions.</p>	<p>Titan</p> <p>Titan's surface is full of dunes, lakes, plains, plateaus, and even craters very similar to those that exist on Earth; Furthermore, as on Earth, stable liquid bodies were found on its surface; which undoubtedly makes it the best place to continue looking for life.</p> <p>Titan's surface supports an atmosphere with a higher pressure than on Earth, approximately 1.5 the pressure that human beings support on Earth.</p> <p>The composition at Titan's surface is mostly molecular nitrogen (90%) and about 5% methane (above 40 km, at the tropopause, methane only accounts for 1.4%).</p>
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THE WEATHER

<p>The climate on Earth in a region depends on many factors, including the amount of sunlight it receives, its altitude, topography, and whether it is close to the oceans. The equator regions receive more sunlight than the poles.</p> <p>On Earth, these same cloud formations exceed 15 km and reach up to 20 km in height, well above the terrestrial tropopause, which is 6 km in winter and reaches 8 km in summer.</p> <p>On Earth, therefore, phenomena of precipitation and evaporation occur. On Earth, processes similar to Titan occur, where the molecules responsible for them are water, while on Titan it is methane.</p>	<p>The climate on Titan includes winds and rains, which create landforms similar to those on Earth, such as dunes, rivers, lakes, seas, probably liquid methane and ethane, the satellite is dominated by patterns seasonal climates as on Earth. With its liquids, both above and below ground, and its robust nitrogen atmosphere, Titan's methane cycle is seen as an analogy to the water cycle.</p> <p>from Earth, albeit at a much lower temperature.</p> <p>On Titan, abundant rainfall occurs at different times of the year, either on the autumn equinox or on the spring equinox, the formation of ethane cirrus clouds has been observed, and the abrupt growth of cumulonimbus clouds that grew between 14 and 25 km, never reaching the height of the tropopause located at approximately 40 km; said formation that could give rise to torrential rains. Either way, even</p>
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	<p>if the rain had been torrential, much of it would have re-evaporated before it hit the ground.</p> <p>Observations made both from Earth and from space by the Hubble Space Telescope and by the instruments aboard the Cassini mission (NASA) and the Huygens descent probe (ESA), have allowed a better understanding of the behavior of Titan's atmosphere, which presents a highly varied and active climate cycle in the troposphere.</p> <p>From the observations made by the Cassini probe, we cannot conclude whether these cumulonimbus clouds on Titan produce torrential methane rains. The methane droplets that survive reevaporation give rise to lakes of dark material that Cassini has indeed observed thanks to a comparison of images acquired at time intervals in which there was a significant formation of clouds of vertical development.</p> <p>The winds on Titan, which should only be a few cm/s (according to the incoming solar radiation), become sustained winds of up to 4 km/h that are amplified to 180 km/h due to the effect of tide that Saturn causes in the satellite.</p> <p>Conditions in Titan's troposphere are such that methane exists in its three states: solid, liquid, and gas. Therefore, phenomena of precipitation, evaporation and probably cryovolcanism occur, which release methane from the surface into the atmosphere.</p> <p>Conditions in the troposphere are such that methane is close to its triple point, where solid, liquid and gaseous states can coexist. In Titan's troposphere, there is a highly varied and active climate cycle.</p>
<p>THE EROSION</p>	
<p>On Earth, soil erosion is usually due to natural causes, such as strong winds or heavy rain. However, its severity increases if various unsustainable human activities are carried out, such as deforestation and poor land management. Erosion alters the chemical composition of the soil, including its nutrients, and therefore has negative consequences for the environment, agricultural production and food safety.</p>	<p>On Titan, the rate of erosion of these formations is very slow, since the rain of methane and other hydrocarbons falls very slowly, and part of it evaporates before touching the tops or the surface.</p> <p>The Huygens probe (ESA) descended on a dry river or lake bed in which the rock images resembled loose, polished pebbles or rock fragments, meaning that there may have been a fluid running across that surface and that cause erosion.</p>

DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS

When we talk about the terrestrial surface temperature, we are referring to the amount of energy that the earth absorbs, we are not referring to the thermal sensation or environmental or air temperature, which is what we perceive when we feel hot or cold. The terrestrial surface temperature (TST) is a parameter that largely complements the measurements of the environmental temperature; the values of the terrestrial surface temperature depend on factors such as vegetation cover and soil moisture.

In this regard, between Earth and Titan there is an important difference, the surface temperature on Saturn's moon is 93.5 °K (-180 °C). The amount of solar radiation that reaches the satellite, together with the greenhouse effect, the result of gases that heat its surface, is minimal and the net result is a satellite that is too cold.

The Goddard Institute for Space Studies, from NASA, in studies carried out, determined that the average surface temperature of the earth is 15.38 °C, However, the surface temperature of the earth is increasing at different points of it, while in the United States it is approximately -40°C, in Australia it is close to 46°C.

Some presidents reject the reports of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) on global warming of the Earth, considering such reports on the risks of increasing temperatures on Earth a myth. Is there awareness of what it means that the temperature continues to rise?

According to the IPCC, if global warming due to greenhouse gases increases, between 400 and 800 million people will suffer restrictions in access to water due to extreme droughts in different parts of the Earth, fires will be more common, high temperatures will increase year After year increasing heat waves in urban areas and the risks of flooding in the world will increase by 100% in the next 25 years. In addition, the rise in sea level will affect more than 50 million people in the world.

We must be aware that the conditions that we observe today on the surface of the Titan satellite will be the same conditions that we will see on Earth, where there are more vulnerable areas than others in terms of temperature increase. In this sense, it is necessary to consider the Earth as a system, where what happens at one point affects the entire system.

It is important to facilitate decision-making in the prioritization of actions that lead to the solution of said situation and result in better living conditions on the earth's surface. The solution to this situation is in our hands, international agreements and reports from climate change experts indicate that public administrations, companies and citizens must contribute to the solution.

TO REFLECT

Titan is a completely strange satellite, its rocks are water, its rivers and seas are liquid methane, its gravity is only 15% of Earth's, but its atmosphere is 45% denser. On Titan the nitrogen composition of the air is generally the same as on Earth, but its oxygen composition is replaced by methane. Instead of clouds, there is a thick formation of brownish-orange haze. There the sunlight is so dim that the entire satellite is in the equivalent of our dawn or sunset. Titan is a strange but fascinating world.

QUESTIONS FOR READERS

What kind of spacesuit are we going to need on Titan?

Where is it on Titan, the vast reservoir of liquid methane? How is methane recycled?

Where and how often does it rain on Titan?

If they had an oxidizing agent on the Cassini probe, could they ignite methane gas?

Will it be 5 billion years in the future when the sun becomes a red giant, so that this moon can have life?

Could some kind of probe be made that could float on the surface of methane oceans?

Is it possible to observe our shadow moving on the surface of the titan?

Will Saturn and the planet's other moons be visible from Titan's surface?

Will we find such beautiful beaches on Titán, like those of Barú? or Vegetation like that of the desert of the guajira in Colombia? If this is what Titan's atmosphere looks like from the Cassini probe, wouldn't we better take care of the Earth for future generations?

IN CONCLUSION

Titan and Earth share some similarities in terms of their structure, their atmosphere, they have broadly similar meteorology, but with some differences.

The characteristics of this satellite of Saturn invite us to hope for extraterrestrial life, you can sit down to think and wonder about the possibility of life, you can also enjoy an environment simulated by the Cassini probe, in which some light breezes were observed, hurricane gusts of wind, rain that falls very, very slowly and invites you to dream, storm clouds of some gases that rise to a great height, large plains with thistles and dunes and some low mountains, as if it were crossing the Guajira desert in Colombia.

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